

DEVELOPMENT OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF USING GAMES IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

The article mainly deals with notions of intercultural competence and its role in teaching English. Using games for the development of intercultural communication skills are investigated.

In the modern world, people are increasingly faced with the need to cooperate with representatives of other cultures. Therefore, knowledge of the language of international communication is an integral aspect by which a person's success and education are judged. Of course, teaching English should be based on respect, understanding and acceptance of cultural differences between the native country and the country of the language being studied. It is this thesis that underlies the intercultural approach to teaching foreign languages.

The Uzbek people have a rich and diverse culture. This is the result of the harmony of the culture of many ancient peoples. Traditions in the regions of Uzbekistan differ from each other. It is possible to find out without error where a particular region or city has its own clothes, art schools, music, which is only pleasant, and even based on the dialect of the interlocutor's dialect. There are a lot of

distinctive differences between English and Uzbek cultures. English culture is diverse and humour, tradition and good manners are characteristics commonly associated with English people. In the modern world, quite high requirements are imposed on a graduate of a linguistic university. In addition to proficiency in a foreign language at the proper level, he must also be a specialist in intercultural communication. Thus it is worth learning and teaching intercultural communication to students.

Recently, methodologists such as Vereshchagin E. M., Furmanova V. P., Ter-Minasova S. G. and Shchukin A. N. have been increasingly talking about the importance of effective use of an intercultural approach. They emphasize that it is thanks to this approach to teaching that a teacher can provide schoolchildren with sufficient knowledge necessary in communicating

representatives of different countries and peoples.

The close relationship between language and culture is obvious. As S.G. Ter-Minasova points out, "language is a mirror of culture, it reflects not only the real world surrounding a person, not only the real conditions of his life, but also the social consciousness of the people, their mentality, national character, lifestyle, traditions, customs, morality, value system, attitude, vision of the world" [1, 8]. (Тер-Минасова, С.Г. Язык и межкультурная коммуникация [Текст] / С.Г. Тер-Минасова. – М.: Слово/ Slovo, 2000. – 261 с)

Intercultural communication is a set of specific processes of interaction between people belonging to different cultures and speaking different languages. It occurs between interaction partners who not only belong to different cultures, but at the same time are aware of the fact that each of them is "different" and each perceives the alienness of the "partner" [5, 11].

Another kind of intercultural communication is cross-cultural communication, which differs from intercultural communication in that it studies the processes during which individuals structure their ideas, expectations and build their behavior in relation to the social environment on their basis [2, 378].

The need for a deeper study of the world of native speakers today is one of the urgent problems in teaching a foreign language. The European concept of teaching foreign languages in recent decades has put forward intercultural competence as a learning goal. According to existing theories, language is proposed to be considered both as an object of study

and as a means of learning. Learning a foreign language involves not separating aspects of language and types of speech activity, but their integration - learning everything at the same time around the cultural context [1].

Intercultural learning is the organization of the educational process, which is based on verbal interaction of representatives of different cultures, the purpose of which is to study the characteristics of another country, and ultimately to understand their uniqueness through the characteristics of other countries based on comparison [3, 56].

To successfully communicate with native speakers, a student studying foreign languages requires a certain amount of background knowledge. It is impossible to learn a language as a means of communication without understanding the way of thinking of the people with whom you are going to interact. It is necessary to have an idea of the history of the country of the language being studied, its state, social and economic structure, customs and traditions. Therefore, in order to provide students with the necessary background knowledge, the study and teaching of languages should be conducted in such a way that at the same time they get acquainted with the culture of the country of the language being studied. The presence of background knowledge and the ability to apply them adequately will serve as a sign of the formation of intercultural communicative competence. If an English teacher, along with teaching the language, gradually explains English folk culture to students using various examples, then in the future, students will achieve a better understanding of each other in the process of productive communication with the

peoples of other peoples. For example, a positive attitude towards another culture and its bearers; the ability to correctly interpret the partner's linguistic behavior; the ability to initiate and maintain an intercultural dialogue; the ability to see similarities and differences between communicating cultures and apply them in the context of intercultural communication; the ability to avoid or resolve cross-cultural conflicts and contradictions, rejection of prejudices and stereotypes; the ability to operate with various verbal and non-verbal means to achieve mutual understanding between cultures; the ability to consciously vary the choice of speech operations depending on the goals and situation of communication, to choose the right style of speech and language means and so on.

The teachers should make extensive use of various interactive methods, games and authentic materials to make his lessons more interesting and contribute to the development of students' intercultural competence.

Games help not only to diversify the lesson, make it interesting, motivate students to learn a foreign language, but also allow them to easily understand the cultural characteristics of the country of the language being studied. More information about the use of game techniques in the context of an intercultural approach to teaching English will be discussed in the next chapter.

Let's consider a description of some forms of gaming activity that can be used in high school classes. Simulation games combine elements such as cooperation, competition. Participants of this game can evaluate their ability to work in a team and show analytical, leadership and other business qualities. The essence of the role-

playing game is the transformation of the student into a particular character and actions in accordance with the assigned game task. The key educational moment in such games is precisely the process of reincarnation, that is, the development of the ability to look at the world through the eyes of another person.

To improve cross-cultural competence, lessons that simulate situations that may happen to a guest of another country during a trip or excursion are most effective. Role-playing games, contests, quizzes come to the rescue. Game techniques provide a higher degree of cognitive independence for students compared to traditional methods, there is a transition from the position of the object of learning to the position of the subject of activity and communication. In addition to plot-role-playing games, games with rules, creative games, for example, design, dramatization and others are used.

Each lesson should be well planned and have its own plot, and all actions in the lesson should correspond to its purpose. Thus, the cognitive activity of students becomes the most effective. Other means that ensure the greatest activity of students in the classroom are: motivation of tasks performed by students; the use of various types of speech activity: dialogue, monologue; the use of visual materials; staging; saturation of the material with new vocabulary, use of various forms of cognitive activity (group, team, pair, etc.); differentiated approach to students; comfortable and creative atmosphere in the classroom. Thus, each student's action during the lesson should correspond to the purpose of the lesson and be communicatively directed: it is necessary not just to ask questions on the topic.

Thus, the game is an effective way to improve the quality and productivity of teaching a foreign language. The use of various games gives good results, allow

students to focus their attention on the main thing – mastering speech skills in a natural conversational situation.

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